

IMPULSE

IMmersive digitisation: uPcycling cULTural
heritage towards new reviving StratEgies

Deliverable D5.1:

Communication & Dissemination
Strategy

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable D5.1(28) articulates IMPULSE project's Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Strategy. Starting by introducing its main goals, the report provides an overview of IMPULSE's C&D Landscape, identifying target audiences at different scales and levels of expertise. This allows the formulation of four communication and dissemination streams of action, connected with specific channels and tools to achieve C&D goals. Furthermore, a C&D management process is introduced, delivering the collaborative approach to communication and dissemination activities: the C&D Team, consisting of representatives of each partner, will work together to nurture the flow of information to make communication a transversal endeavor.

Lastly, the report introduces the IMPULSE C&D Toolkit, a set of visual guidelines and templates conveying IMPULSE's visual identity, to ensure coherence and visibility to the project.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary

Abbreviations and Acronyms

1. Introduction

- 1.1. IMPULSE Project
- 1.2. Objectives of the Work Package 5
- 1.3. Objectives of Task 5.1 and D28
- 1.4. Our approach for a sustainable, inclusive, and equal Communication and Dissemination process

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

- 2.1. Preliminary work
- 2.2. Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy
- 2.3. Communication and Dissemination Landscape
 - 2.3.1. Target Audiences and areas of influence
- 2.4. Communication and Dissemination aims
 - 2.4.1. Key concepts
 - 2.4.2. Tone of Voice
 - 2.4.3. Taglines and list of hashtags
 - 2.4.4. Languages
- 2.5. Communication and Dissemination Management Process
 - 2.4.1. Timeline
 - 2.4.2. Collaborative model
 - 2.4.3. Communication & Dissemination Team Responsibilities
 - 2.4.4. Monitoring

3. Channels

- 3.1. IMPULSE Communication Channels
 - 3.1.1. IMPULSE Website
 - 3.1.2. IMPULSE Social Media Channels
 - IMPULSE Collaborative space
 - Extra channels: Acceleration Mentoring Hub & Metaverse
- 3.2. External booster channels
 - 3.2.1. Partners' channels

3.3. E-Newsletter

3.4. Events

3.4.1 C&D Event Form

4. Communication and Dissemination Toolkit

4.1. Visual Identity

4.1.1. Logo

4.1.2. Colour Scheme

4.1.3. Typography

4.1.4. Templates

4.2. Data-based artifacts protocol

2 Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
Dx	Deliverable number X
WPx	Work Package number X
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
CH	Cultural Heritage
CCSI	Cultural and Creative Sector Industries
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EITC&C	European Institute of Innovation & Technology - Culture & Creativity

1 Introduction

1.1 IMPULSE Project: short introduction

Digital technologies can help to disclose immersive pathways for IMPULSE to shape stories of sustainable futures out of our multifaceted heritage.

However, the issue of accessibility, cross-implementation and usage of already-digitised content raises major concerns in the European cultural heritage digitisation processes. Thanks to a holistic approach, **IMPULSE - IMmersive digitisation: uPcycling cULTural heritage towards new reviving StratEgies** - strives for more engaging modes of interaction, supporting the upcycling of existing digitised cultural heritage content in immersive contexts. Here, the project will address interoperability challenges between platforms, enhancing their integration into such emerging spaces as the Metaverse. This includes pioneering standardisation processes and updating legal frameworks to align with contemporary transformations in education, arts, and the Creative and Cultural Industries Sector (CCSI).

IMPULSE will expand the role of artifacts in digital exhibition environments, inviting collective, embodied, and engaging interactions through diverse perspectives and unsung narratives. This approach aims to engage a broader audience and include underrepresented communities, offering deeper insights into displayed themes through artistic expressions such as visual arts and dance within IMPULSE's pilot programs and prototypes.

IMPULSE will engage with a wide range of stakeholders - researchers, artists, cultural heritage professionals, CCSIs, entrepreneurs, local institutions, and companies -, through the establishment of a dynamic ecosystem, and as the result of synergic initiatives such as the IMPULSE Community of Practice, the IMPULSE Hackathon, and the Acceleration & Mentoring Hub. These platforms will contribute to the development and establishment of a broader European network, where partners and other interested experts, institutions and professionals will be able to access, discuss and build on the project's achievements and findings.

1.2 Objectives of the Work Package 5

The IMPULSE project achieves its goals through a strategic plan, made of six Work Packages (WPs). WPs work as building blocks, each with its own purpose to channel progress and catalyse a lasting impact. A Pert chart is used to summarise and visually present the main building blocks of the IMPULSE project.

Figure 1. Visualisation showing IMPULSE's WPs and their interactions. WP5 DISS is represented as a WP crossing other WPs activities, providing them with content-amplifying strategies to diffuse their main achievements.

Within IMPULSE, WP5 is dedicated to dissemination and communication activities, aiming to establish connections among actors involved in cultural heritage digitisation. Here, communication and engagement activities will be used to facilitate dialogue and participation.

WP5 will foster a community for 3D digitisation and subsequent fair use of objects, adopting innovative communication tools and supporting interplay among networks and platforms. WP5 will also contribute to relevant EU programs and promote project sustainability and dissemination.

The illustration highlights the horizontal configuration of WP5, with dissemination and communication being framed as transversal processes, integrated with all WPs and partners' activities. **WP5's operational timeframe covers M1 to M36, unfolding along the project's Milestones and Deliverables.**

This framework invites **a collaborative approach to IMPULSE's dissemination and communication strategy**, which will be **designed by WP5 lead partner, UNIBO**. With the support of all the partners, UNIBO will develop a mediating infrastructure (real and digital) to orient and build relationships inside and outside IMPULSE, to contribute to the international culture, creativity, and humanities debate around digitised Cultural Heritage.

Dissemination and communication will go beyond institutional communication, activating co-design initiatives capable of involving different players to identify the right channels and the most effective messages for the project's results.

The adoption of a multi-level communication (addressed to institutions, citizens, creatives, cultural players, students, etc.) will promote a horizontal approach in the co-production of CCS content, initiatives, products and services between IMPULSE and territories involved by the project.

The overarching goal of WP5 is to enable connections among researchers, artists, CH practitioners, CCIs, local institutions and companies through a profiled and effective engagement of the different actors. Accordingly, communication activities are coupled with engagement and empowerment activities in this WP to define the most appropriate tools and channels to effectively dialogue with the involved subjects. The scope is to support participants as active and informed members of a growing community aiming at a full 3D digitisation of cultural heritage and fair use of digitised objects.

The related objectives of this WP are:

- to define and adopt innovative and disruptive communication tools to increase bottom-up participation in the prototyping phase of the project and boost the connection among freelancers, artists, researchers and CCIs in the CH sector.
- to support the interplay among existing digitisation networks and platforms, fostering the project sustainability and dissemination of results to share and contribute to EU programs and initiatives relevant for cultural heritage and its digitisation (such as ECCCH) and with the EIT Culture & Creativity KIC in the cultural and creative sector.

WP5's main objectives are:

- to provide feedback to the target groups, including scientists.
- to communicate its results to a wider audience, avoiding stereotypes.
- to influence policies with data-based evidence and to establish a mentoring process to extend the action's impact, provide a meaningful and user-friendly introduction to the Metaverse.
- to facilitate the design of Communication and Dissemination activities.

According to the objectives illustrated above, the following table lists C&D tasks and deliverables, specifying timeframes and partners involved.

Tasks	Description	Timeframe	Partners
T5.1	Communication & Dissemination Strategy	M1-M3	UNIBO ; All
T5.1.1	Launch of the Call for Interest during the Kick-Off in Kraków	M4	UNIBO
T5.1.2	Setting up the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo)	M4-M8	UNIBO ; All
T5.2	From engagement to empowerment process	M4-M8	UNIBO ; All
T5.2.1	Developing and launching the IMCo working space on Mastodon	M4	UNIBO ; NKUA
T5.3	Roadmap Strategy: the Pre-Hackathon phase	M8-M24	UNIBO ; All
T5.3.1	IMCo Workshop in Leuven: focus on Academia	M10	KU Leuven ; All
T5.3.2	IMCo Workshop in Malta: focus on Artists	M18	UM ; All
T5.3.3	IMCo Workshop in Saarbrücken: focus on CCSIs	M26	K8, CER ; All
T5.4	IMPULSE Hackathon	M28	UNIBO, NKUA ; All
T5.5	Exploitation Plan & cross - fertilization opportunities with other projects	M1-M36	UM, Heritage Malta ; All
T5.5.1	Creation of an Acceleration & Mentoring Hub for the most innovative projects selected during the Hackathon	M30	JU, FBKW ; All
T5.6	Final Conference in Bologna	M33	UNIBO ; All
Deliv.	Description	Timeframe	
D28	Joint document outlining the dissemination and communication strategy of IMPULSE	M3	
D29	Call for the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo) to select participants from the target groups	M4	
D30	Set-up of the digital co-working space of IMCo on Mastodon and IMPULSE website	M8	
D31	Operational plan documenting the strategy for exploiting projects results and impacts	M30	
D32	Acceleration&Mentoring Hub for best 5 projects deriving from the Hackathon developed with the 3 prototypes	M30	
MS18	Pre-Hackathon Phase: IMCo Workshops 5	M10; M18; M26	
MS19	IMPULSE Hackathon	M28	
MS20	IMPULSE Final Conference	M33	

Table 1. List of tasks, deliverables and milestones already connected with WP5 in project's proposal or not explicitly connected to WP5 but with potential for C&D aims and activities (i.e. milestones).

In conclusion, WP5 will deliver:

- **an overall project communication and dissemination strategy plan** that outlines the communication channels (press, project website, newsletters, social media, events), according to an intersectional perspective. Dissemination will be supported by Partners' channels (i.e. Cluster Create, European Creative Hubs Network, UNA EUROPA, UNIVERSEUM, Civis Alliance, CIVIS alliance, Onassis Foundation Stegi, Thessaloniki Film Festival, Greek Museum of Contemporary Art, EIT C&C, EFAP - European Forum of Advanced Practices, SAR - Society of Artistic Research, European University of the Seas). The strategy will build on the IMPULSE Consortium's experience in engaging and empowering CCI organisations, artists and academic communities.
- **a tailor-made strategy** combining 'who' (clusters of targets), 'what' (specific outcomes) and 'how' (channels and tools) in a timeline. The links with existing CCI groups (at all levels), trade associations, research departments, education realms, cultural heritage agencies, artists and decision-makers at different levels will favour combined communication/dissemination activities (i.e. training programs, workshops, a community of practice, hackathons, etc.) to optimise the impact at the local scale.
- **transnational dissemination through joint initiatives and events** managed in synergy with the EIT C&C initiatives (leverage of UNIBO, JU, KUL, K8, Una Europa which are partners of the EIT C&C) to create a critical mass generating additional synergies for a cross-borders innovation culture on digitisation. Visibility will be ensured via the official partners' websites, the periodical newsletters, and a wide social media outreach.
- **physical interactive dissemination events** will be organised by the partners by developing a roadmap dissemination strategy (pre-hackathon phase) that will culminate with a final event (IMPULSE Hackathon) organised in M28 shaped as a two-day open event taking place in Athens (GR). Representatives from the Community of Practice and other practitioners will participate and bring the experience developed to Prototype new ideas and give feedback on the project's outcome. The Hackathon will comprise a more institutional part where the Advisory Board and EU representatives will be hosted; and a more informal part where participants will co-design activities open to the public. The Hackathon will also be streamed online (i.e., using Twitch and YouTube) to attract media attention and remote audiences. Kick-off and final meeting. There will be two Metaverse exhibitions / performances emerging from work package 1. The performance piece will be shown in three forms – on site, online and in VR. The event will take place as a public live event on site (in Malta), streamed online in-browser for the international audience, and later viewed in VR for the locally present and international audience for the

duration of the exhibition. The exhibition piece is a Metaverse space (online only) that invites visitors to reflect on didactics and participation in historical and contemporary cultural heritage interpretation in the context of teacher-student co-creation.

- **Acceleration & Mentoring Hub** for the most innovative projects selected during the Hackathon; to maximise the impact of the project after its duration, the project will mentor the best 5 projects proposed during the Hackathon to be developed in synergy with the 3 IMPULSE prototypes, in their start-up phase (T5.5.1).
- **a plurality of dissemination tools and channels** further described in the Communication & Dissemination Strategy (C&D Strategy).

1.3 Objectives of Task 5.1 and D28

This document concerns Task 5.1 – Communication & Dissemination Strategy (C&D Strategy) edited by UNIBO, in collaboration with all partners throughout the timeframe M1-M3.

C&D Strategy defines the objectives, the target audiences as well as the channels and the specific tools, providing a framework for targeted communication campaigns around the milestones. C&D Strategy includes sub-objectives and responsibilities for each partner according to its role, business activity, existing connections, and joint dissemination actions for EU and local levels. Online tools will be complemented by:

- targeted policy advocacy and recommendation activities.
- Hackathon and final conference.
- dissemination at major EU/national/regional events, and symposia by academic networks.
- scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals (open access); articles in the specialized press.
- workshops and meeting with the IMPULSE Community of practice.

Communication activities started at M1 when project's visual identity has been established, the website is live, and social media channels are created and continue throughout the lifetime of the project, with measurable targets and KPIs (i.e. awareness-raising and audiences reached) set by UNIBO in the Communication & Dissemination Strategy (D28).

Particularly, the purpose of Deliverable 28 – Joint document outlining the dissemination and communication strategy of IMPULSE – is:

- to define objectives, target groups and channels for Impulse's communication, dissemination.
- to describe the methods used in project promotion, interaction, and dissemination.
- to encourage project partners to adopt project key messages, tone-of-voice, channels, and IMPULSE toolkit.
- to offer a strategic basis and tools for detailed communication, dissemination process.

1.4 Our approach for a sustainable, inclusive, and equal Communication and Dissemination process

At the heart of IMPULSE is a vision of a European immersive digitisation driven by culture and creativity, upcycled technology, vivid storytelling, and digital protocols standardisation.

Within such a vision, IMPULSE stands committed to the interplay of technological innovation and cultural enrichment, following the principles of sustainability as main drivers of change. **This dedication is reflected in IMPULSE's communication and dissemination strategies. As lead partners of WP5, UNIBO recognises the importance of integrating sustainability principles into all aspects of communication and dissemination activities.** IMPULSE is committed to upholding the following principles and practices to ensure the sustainability of the project's communication and dissemination strategy and outputs:

- **Environmentally Responsible Communication Practices:** IMPULSE will strive to minimise the environmental impact of communication and dissemination activities by reducing paper usage, promoting digital communication channels, and implementing eco-friendly practices in the production and distribution of materials. The prioritisation of digital over physical media contributes to lowering the carbon footprint of our activities.
- **Inclusive and Diverse Storytelling:** IMPULSE is dedicated to fostering diversity, equity, and inclusion in our communication and dissemination strategies. We will ensure that our messaging is accessible to all stakeholders, regardless of background or ability, and that our outreach efforts are inclusive and representative of diverse perspectives. Sustainability in cultural heritage is not just about environmental considerations but also about social equity and inclusivity. Our communication strategy involves telling diverse and inclusive stories of cultural heritage, ensuring that voices from all sections of society are heard, and their heritage is preserved and shared. By doing so, we contribute to a more equitable and sustainable cultural narrative.
- **Ethical Engagement:** IMPULSE will uphold the highest standards of integrity and ethical conduct in all our communication and dissemination activities. This includes being transparent and honest in our messaging, respecting the privacy and rights of individuals, and avoiding the dissemination of misinformation or harmful content.
- **Long-Term Engagement and Impact:** IMPULSE recognizes that the success of the project depends on sustained engagement and support from stakeholders. Therefore, we will develop communication and dissemination strategies that prioritize building long-term relationships and fostering ongoing dialogue among involved stakeholders and with the projects' target audiences. Furthermore, through our various channels, we aim to inform and inspire stakeholders about sustainable practices in the digitisation and re-use of digitised cultural heritage. This involves sharing best practices, research findings, and success stories that highlight the intersection of technology, culture, and sustainability. As such, dissemination and communication activities will contribute in setting "resonating

conditions” for organisations and projects working with digitised cultural heritage to approach IMPULSE’s partnership and foster loops of collaboration. Through these collaborations, we aim to amplify IMPULSE’s message and findings, nurturing the establishment of a dedicated community of practice.

- **Continuous Improvement:** IMPULSE is committed to evaluating and improving our communication and dissemination efforts to maximise their effectiveness and minimise their environmental footprint. This includes soliciting feedback from stakeholders, monitoring key performance indicators, and adapting our strategies based on lessons learned.

By linking our activities to these principles, we aim to not only effectively communicate the objectives and outcomes of the IMPULSE project, but also to contribute to the broader goals of sustainability and social responsibility, through a collaborative and participative approach.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

According to the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program, there are different spheres for research project dissemination and communications activities to be covered. The spheres are:

Communication

Communication means all the activities aiming to make the project and its developments known from the very beginning until the end of the project. Communication includes the project brand and presence in various communication channels.

Dissemination

Dissemination means all the activities that spread information on the project results, via reports, briefs and publications.

IMPULSE's C&D Strategy will consider both spheres of research project communications. The strategy will be developed by UNIBO and contributed by all project partners. It will be updated if needed.

2.1 Preliminary work

Before developing the C&D Strategy, we started preliminary activities such as a survey and initial data collection from partners which later informed the C&D Strategy.

We engaged with IMPULSE partners by designing a survey to be submitted on Microsoft Forms and connected to IMPULSE Workspace, Microsoft Teams. The survey activity, titled "**IMPULSE COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION STRATEGY - Call to Action**", was launched on the 20th of February 2024 as a preliminary step in collecting essential information about partners and outline the project's communication and dissemination landscape (*see section 2.3*).

The survey activity aimed at:

- **Collecting communication material from all partners:** the first section of the survey listed requests about partner general descriptions, brief introductions about the research team, logos, pictures in high resolution.
- **Mapping partners' own channels:** the second section of the survey ventured into partners' existing C&D channels. It listed questions about:
 - C&D contact of reference;
 - Language of preference;
 - Synergies with relevant networks' events (networks and communities already accessible by partners to boost IMPULSE C&D flow);

- Synergies with resonating projects;
- List of IMPULSE foreseen products to be disseminated.

The survey provided core information to align the C&D strategy to the specific needs of the variety of partners involved in the IMPULSE project.

2.2 Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The IMPULSE C&D Strategy aims at increasing awareness and use of digitised cultural heritage in the cultural and creative sectors, while engaging with key stakeholders, promoting project activities, and ensuring long-term accessibility and exploitation of project outputs. As it serves as a cornerstone for effectively sharing the project's progress, results, and main insights, the IMPULSE C&D Strategy is divided into **four main streams** that are closely linked to communication and dissemination objectives: (1) **awareness and visibility raising**, (2) **engaging for inclusivity, cooperation, and collaboration**, (3) **monitoring and assessing impact**, and (4) **ensuring ongoing relevance and accessibility**.

Each stream unfolds along the main deliverables and milestones foreseen in the project's roadmap.

Figure 2. Gantt diagram comparing the timeframes of WP5 main tasks and deliverables, and project milestones eligible for C&D activities, in relation to C&D Streams.

The diagram shows the distribution of events connected to IMPULSE's development and public engagement. They have been understood as key methods of tailoring an adaptive C&D strategy and are structured in streams that overlap and inform each other over time, resulting in a series of actions that will be continuously updated according to communication and dissemination objectives. Such a **stream model** will ensure adaptability of the C&D strategy, and support the creation of tailored content.

STREAM 1: Awareness and visibility-raising

The **first stream (M1-M36)** will be articulated around a pedagogical vision of the project (M1-M8) to gradually convey an image of a recognised, multi-disciplinary expertise, while ensuring that awareness is raised on IMPULSE project and its ecosystem. This stage link to (1) **awareness and visibility-raising**, especially regarding the application of immersive technologies to digitised cultural heritage. By formulating *key messages* and defining the *tone-of-voice*, the C&D Strategy will enhance visibility on IMPULSE, thanks to the combination of a unified branding and core message for coherence and recognisability. Overall, ensuring that project communications are inclusive and accessible to diverse audiences, including non-specialists and underrepresented communities, is a priority. This involves using clear language and leveraging various formats and channels to reach a wide range of audiences. Communication materials will be designed to be adaptable, to resonate with the specific audiences of the different sectors involved in the project, and the different outcomes to be communicated: i.e. best practices, case studies, and innovative approaches to digitisation and upcycling of cultural heritage. We will reach out to a broad audience, ranging from researchers, cultural heritage professionals, the creative and cultural industries (CCIs), policymakers, and the general public.

As the project develops, **the first stream will deploy communication actions and dissemination activities (M9-M36)** that will enhance the results coming from the main milestones and touchpoints (MS18, MS19, MS2, MS3, MS4, MS5, MS6, MS20). These actions respond to (1) **awareness and visibility-raising** by activating a more detailed conversation on IMPULSE, since content creation will be more vertical and milestone-specific. At this stage, the first stream will also highlight the *multi- and inter-disciplinary* of stakeholders involved in IMPULSE. The project's ambitions tap into diverse disciplinary domains, ranging from immersive digitisation to artistic media and processes, connected to cultural and creative professional and educational contexts. It is essential to communicate the interplay of the plurality of expertise that IMPULSE brings together to address digital transformation and intervene in some of the major gaps of European cultural heritage digitisation processes.

The second stage of the first stream sets a series of communication and dissemination actions for broader expert and non-expert engagement, facilitating results exchange with various multi-level audiences at different stages of the project.

STREAM 2: Engaging for inclusivity, cooperation, and collaboration

The **second stream (M6-M36)** links to (2) **engaging for inclusivity, cooperation, and collaboration**, implementing a series of actions aiming at creating bridges between partners and key stakeholders of the IMPULSE projects, including academic institutions, cultural heritage organisations, and the creative sector. Along this stream, virtual spaces will be developed and launched to support the creation of the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo): such spaces will invite participation, exchange of ideas, perspectives, and insights, while delivering key touchpoint information linked to specific events, as shown in the diagram above.

Particularly, the second stream will be activated in tight connection with key Deliverables and Milestones, starting with the launch of the Collaborative space to set up the IMCo (D30), and concurrently with the delivery of workshops (MS18), of the Hackaton (MS19), of the Mentoring Hub (D32), of the launch of running pilot and delivery of prototypes (MS2, MS3, MS4), of the Metaverse performance and exhibition (MS5, MS6), and, lastly, of the final conference in Bologna (MS20).

The second stream informs the first stream, expanding the pedagogical & communication vision with the possibility to gather insights directly from stakeholders. The second stream provides the opportunity to amplify the networks and ecosystem IMPULSE is already connected with, inviting a broader conversation on different levels to catalyse enhanced collaboration in the IMPULSE's Communication & Dissemination Landscape ([see section 2.3](#)). As IMPULSE builds on the existing knowledge and capacity of its partners, activities, and networks, it establishes links and synergies with related efforts such as relevant actions funded by Horizon Europe or Horizon 2020 and the "European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage" calls in the frame of Horizon Europe Cluster 2, as well as with projects funded under the Digital Europe programme to establish a European data space for cultural heritage. Here, culture - including cultural heritage - and digital technologies are framed as key drivers contributing to the sustainability transformation needed to meet the objectives of the European Green Deal and the 2030 Agenda.

Consequently, the second stream of the C&D Strategy will be committed to deliver IMPULSE's positioning within the broader framework of European actions, channelling its efforts into the innovation landscape regarding cultural and creative sectors to tackle digital transformation and transition.

STREAM 3: Monitoring and assessing impact

The **third stream (M1-M36)** responds to (3) **monitoring and assessing impact**, and it is dedicated to setting qualitative and quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor the reach and impact of communication activities. The resulting insights will inform the C&D management process as well as the overall C&D Strategy, contributing to

continuous re-tuning and refinement of Stream 1 and Stream 2 according to the emergent needs.

This will provide the strategy with continuous feedback loops, ensuring that it remains inclusive, dynamic, and responsive to the needs of the project's wide-ranging audience. Key to the third stream is the collaborative management process aiming at facilitating cross-sectoral dialogues and enhancing the multi-disciplinary expertise IMPULSE stems from. Such an approach will provide IMPULSE's communication and dissemination activities with content (key concepts and messages) that has been co-created with involved partners. This extends to KPIs, whose setting will happen through **concerted sessions held with the Communication and Dissemination Management Team** (see [section 2.4](#)) so that the facets the project is made of can be monitored according to their specific features. Such a collaborative and adaptive approach ensures that communication and dissemination actions and materials stay relevant, engaging, and representative of the multifaceted nature of the project's board of partners.

The third stream follows the project throughout its duration (M1-M36), in combination with specific timeframes (M7, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) in which the Communication and Dissemination Management Team will share analytics based on the co-set KPIs and refine the C&D Strategy according to the results achieved compared to the strategy's goals.

STREAM 4: Ensuring ongoing relevance and accessibility

The **fourth stream (M30-M36)** links to (4) **ensuring ongoing relevance and accessibility** of IMPULSE's main results and legacy beyond the lifespan of the project itself. By unfolding in connection to the delivery of the Exploitation Plan (D31), the fourth stream aims to prepare the conditions for the established networks, delivered resources, and launched platforms to be accessible, ensuring the availability of project's main findings and activities, so to foster further conversations and build-up multi-level collaboration on cultural heritage digitisation processes.

2.3 Communication and Dissemination Landscape

The first step to positioning the project is to understand the landscape in which the dissemination and communication strategy will take place, building on the project's ecosystem of partners and their own specific connections with bodies and networks that might resonate with and benefit from the IMPULSE project.

Figure 3. Visual representation of IMPULSE network organised along scales. Core partners are marked with a blue line. This figure shows the potential outreach of IMPULSE C&D activities.

As the diagram indicates, **IMPULSE's landscape unfolds at different scales through different actors**, connecting expertise coming from academia, public bodies, and industries working within the cultural and creative sector. Here, IMPULSE's ecosystem of partners (marked in light blue) is represented together with associations, networks, and bodies they are already connected with on a local, national and European level. This provides a more detailed overview of IMPULSE's positioning and its potential outreach. Within the resulting landscape, UNIBO and all partners can actively work to maximise synergies with cultural heritage and Academic Institutions, policymakers, CCI organisations, civil society organisations and other stakeholders at the EU level - i.e.

Cluster Create, European Creative Hubs Network, UNA EUROPA, UNIVERSEUM, Civis Alliance, CIVIS alliance, Onassis Foundation Stegi, Thessaloniki Film Festival, Greek Museum of Contemporary Art, EIT Culture & Creativity, EFAP - European Forum of Advanced Practices, SAR - Society of Artistic Research, European University of the Seas. Furthermore, UNIBO, KU Leuven, JU as part of UnaEuropa Alliance have strong relations with EU institutions, regional representation offices in Brussels, relevant European associations, and thematic networks - *i.e. Culture Action Europe, Trans Europe Halles.*

Communication & Dissemination activities will be tailored to different targets in **three main groups**, with different specificities and needs. Each group will be addressed by using different tools and communication channels.

The first group is connected to project collaboration among IMPULSE partners. The C&D Strategy for this sphere is connected to adopting the most suitable channels and tools to maximise collaboration.

The second group relates to specialized public, interested and active on the topics of cultural heritage, is digitisation, immersive technologies, and Culture & Creativity. Target profiles are described in [section 2.3.1](#). The C&D Strategy for this sphere is related to fostering interest in IMPULSE project and to engage them in co-creation activities such as surveys, workshops etc. Part of this sphere of actors is the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo), who will aggregate people with different backgrounds and skills in the usage of digital cultural heritage in dedicated hackathons. A dedicated IMCo collaborative space will be activated after a careful analysis of existing tools and channels (e.g. Discord, Slack, etc; [see section 3.5](#)). More details on the characteristics of the collaborative space, along with a description of the prototyping process to better define it, will be included in D29.

The third group relates to the wider public, including citizens interested in having updates on IMPULSE actions and activities. The C&D strategy for this sphere of actors is connected to disseminate updates, results, and to foster a wider knowledge building process.

2.2.1 Target Audiences and areas of influence

A key aspect of the C&D Strategy is the clear definition of the target audiences, which will be addressed according to the level of communications that is needed to engage with. According to the three main spheres of actors introduced above, target audiences of communication and dissemination actions fall into the second sphere of actors, the one relating to **specialized public, interested and active on the topics of cultural heritage, digitisation, immersive technologies, and Culture&Creativity**. Particularly, **target audiences are defined** in compliance with WP1 elaboration **along five categories**:

1. Scientists, researchers, academics, students

Relevance: growing evidence of new processes of digitisation in academia and dissemination of the IMPULSE prototyped devoted to educational purposes.

Area of influence (Innovation Domain): Scientific Advancement on digitised CH upcycling and on the integration of immersive technologies. Connection with education in terms of future literacy.

2. Policy makers, decision-makers, European networks

Relevance: increase future interoperability and provide recommendations for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH).

Area of influence (Innovation Domain): New policies definition, new rules for upcycling, opportunities to create a critical mass to influence future funding schemes.

3. CCSI organisations and networks, freelancers, designers, and artists

Relevance: increase awareness of CCI potential among different sectors to generate creative-based.

Area of influence (Innovation Domain): Technology Advancement, Cross-fertilization with performative arts, etc. Economic innovation in the definition of new possible markets.

4. GLAMs (Galleries, libraries, archives, museums, cultural heritage holders of humanities materials)

Relevance: preserve humanities collections that facilitate research, strengthen teaching, and provide opportunities for lifelong learning.

Area of influence (Innovation Domain): Cultural and social innovation: new accessibility opportunities; Management innovation: a shared protocol to manage CH data and digitised contents.

5. Non-users, individuals who do not use new information technologies, products or services, either because they are not familiar with them or because they do not perceive the environment and the facilities offered as suitable, adequate or accessible.

Relevance: IMPULSE includes a group of potential and future users, specifically those in heritage contexts where XR apps would be applicable, but who currently lack the knowledge to integrate such approaches into their work, to create new audiences and new market potential for CH upcycling.

Area of influence: Socio-economic innovation: increased capacity building through new training modules to reduce the digital gap about XR applications; mindset changes relating to new technologies integration; implemented awareness of digitisation opportunities for preservation and adding value to CH.

2.4 Communication and Dissemination aims

IMPULSE main communication aims are:

- **COMM1. Promoting and raising awareness and interest in the project**, its progress and results as well as themes related to immersive digital experiences connected to digitised cultural heritage, and the possibilities to upcycled digitised content to allow the emergence of “unsung” narratives.
- This overarching aim can be broken down into a list of sub-goals, allowing for a more detailed development of specific communication and dissemination activities to support the project’s main areas of interest: **Education; Creation; Connection**. Particularly **COMM1** relies on:
- **COMM1.1. Contributing to sharing knowledge on the theme of accessibility of culture and cultural heritage in digital spaces**, understood as a key driver in fostering innovation in the cultural and creative sectors as the cultural heritage sector, together with the rest of society, finds itself in the midst of a dramatic digital transition.
- **COMM1.2. Establishing a common scaffolding to map out and intercept all the IMPULSE target groups (and out-of-target groups)**. This will benefit from interactions with WP1 and WP2, especially regarding the setting-up of the Community of Practice.
→ [IMCO Implementation](#)
- **COMM1.3. Weaving a compelling storytelling around the digitised collections** available to the project and related immersive experiences when integrated into the project’s prototypes.
→ Communication channels
- **COMM1.4. Tapping into the projects’ key concepts** such as integration of Humanities, Future Literacy and Upcycling and Scaling strategies linked to digitised content.
→ [New learning modules](#)
- **COMM2. Fostering multidisciplinary interaction and understanding among stakeholders** about their needs and the project’s final benefits to them, to ensure the usability of the results. Particularly, Comm2 relies on:
- **COMM2.1. Creating spaces for practitioners in the field of digitisation, education**, together with creatives, artists and CCSI stakeholders to connect, dismantling creative and technological silos and exploring interplays to research and innovation and (re)use of collections.
→ [Pre-Hackathon workshops and Hackathons](#)

- **COMM2.2. *Creating opportunities for stakeholders to co-create and discover*** together novel uses of digital heritage archives in contexts such as the Metaverse.
→ [New IMPULSE prototypes](#)

IMPULSE's dissemination aims can be formulated as follows:

- **DISS1. *Sharing knowledge and recommendations with specialized audience linked to research and innovation.*** These efforts aim to promote IMPULSE's outcomes as building blocks for further cultural heritage digitization processes, fostering ongoing dialogue and collaboration in relevant research and innovation areas. Particularly, DISS1 relies on:
 - **DISS1.1. *Publishing peer-reviewed articles based on research and development work carried out within the IMPULSE project.*** All partners will look for call for papers and call for contributions, as opportunities to present, diffuse, and discuss the project's milestones and relevant outcomes with the scientific community. The Communication and Dissemination Team will keep track of the participated calls and formalize these activities in a dedicated section in D31 – Exploitation plan.
 - **DISS1.2. *Engaging policymakers by providing recommendations on immersive digital experiences*** connected to digitized cultural heritage. These briefs will highlight the societal and cultural significance of preserving and promoting digitized cultural heritage through immersive digital experiences, emphasizing the potential economic, educational, and social benefits for creative practitioners and experts, as well society at large.

→ [Policy briefs](#)

- **DISS2. *Enhancing capability building*** among researchers, artists, cultural heritage practitioners, CCSIs, entrepreneurs, local institutions, companies, and other relevant stakeholders, through a profiled and effective engagement such as IMPULSE Community of Practice, and appropriate tools and channels such as IMPULSE Hackathon and Acceleration & Mentoring Hub in order to facilitate effective dialogue, co-creation and capacity building in immersive digitisation.

→ [IMPULSE Community of Practice](#)

→ [Appropriate tools and channels such as IMPULSE Hackathon and Acceleration & Mentoring Hub](#)

- **DISS3. *Making the project results available*** for exploitation beyond the lifetime of the project.

→ [IMPULSE Hackathon and Acceleration & Mentoring Hub](#)

2.4.1 Co-designed Key Concepts

Key Concepts embody the multi-disciplinary facets of IMPULSE expertise. By collecting inputs from all the partners involved, the C&D Team – a team made of WP5 lead partner UNIBO and representatives of all partners (see section 2.4.3) - will be able to tailor key messages, draw out key hashtags, and weave compelling narratives that align with the diversity of knowledge flowing into IMPULSE, establishing a trans-disciplinary foundation. Key concepts will be set and co-defined in online collaborative sessions (brainstorming on a dedicated Miro board) with the C&D Team to engage with target audiences, discussing the priority and verticality of the messages to be delivered, in connection to the C&D Strategy's Stream 1: Awareness and visibility raising (see section 2.2).

Following a brainstorming session, key concepts were co-defined on the following main themes:

- **Digital Cultural Heritage: the integration of STEM sciences and humanities.**
- **The Metaverse: an experience, a mode to participate in CH co-creation, a development challenge.**
- **Upcycling strategies linked to creativity and digital cultural heritage.**
- **Future Literacy: fostering anticipation, imagination, and speculative approaches.**
- **Empowering diverse communities: co-creation and the future of higher education.**
- **Advancing policy and legal frameworks in enhancing digital cultural heritage.**

Each theme was discussed by the C&D Team and unpacked in key concepts along two scales:

1. **The verticality of expertise needed to approach the theme:** this scale was connected to IMPULSE's five categories of target audiences, ranging from non-users (low verticality) to GLAMS and CCSI (medium-to high verticality), to policymakers and academia (high verticality, understood here as infrastructural advancements connected to research and innovation). Verticality of expertise is a scale aiming at identifying the target audience needs and main concerns to tune key messages accordingly.
2. **The priority in delivering key concepts to target audiences:** this scale is transversal and aims at providing a scaffold to build the narratives through which Stream 1: Awareness and Visibility raising (see section 2.2) objectives and achievements will be achieved.

The interplay of these two scales allows the formulation of accurate key concepts starting from the main themes representing the multidisciplinary expertise of IMPULSE.

Figure 4. Scatter chart connecting key themes' verticality of expertise with priority of communication. Screenshot taken from the brainstorming session held on Miro Board by the C&D team.

The image above shows a section of the Miro board, where the C&D Team collaborated to articulate key concepts from main themes, adapting them according to the vertical expertise-scale and the priority-scale. The diagram allows the construction of a compelling narrative, tuned to the needs of target audiences, that will directly inform communication and dissemination actions.

The **Miro board** ([accessible here](#)) will be open for the duration of the project, for ongoing input collection from partners. This will provide the C&D Team with a shared space to activate feedback loops and adjust communication and dissemination actions continuously. The link will be also shared in and accessible by the IMPULSE Repository (Teams), under WP5 channel.

2.4.2 Tone of Voice

Setting the *tone of voice* for all IMPULSE communications is an essential step in pursuing consistent and effective communication, in order to effectively resonate with multi-disciplinary and multi-scale target audiences. To achieve this, IMPULSE's tone of voice will be:

- **Inclusive and accessible:** the tone will be welcoming and understandable to a broad audience. It will invite participation and make the content accessible to both specialists and the general public.
- **Inspiring, imaginative, and forward-thinking:** reflecting the innovative breadth of the project, the tone inspires and evokes a sense of progress and future possibilities, particularly in the realm of digital heritage and immersive experiences, nuanced with creativity and thinking-out-of-the-box processes.
- **Educational and informative:** since the project involves a significant educational component, the tone will be informative, providing clear and valuable insights into the project's aims, processes, and outcomes.
- **Inviting and engaging:** the tone encourages collaboration and engagement, resonating with the project's ethos of partnership across different sectors and disciplines.
- **Professional yet approachable:** maintain a balance between excessive specialisation and approachability to ensure credibility while being relatable to a diverse audience.

2.4.3 Taglines and list of hashtags

By adhering to this defined tone of voice and key concepts, the IMPULSE project can invite audiences to its vision, goals, and achievements, ensuring clarity, consistency, and maximum impact across all its communications. As such, the C&D Strategy provides a set of long and short taglines for the five main target audiences:

Scientists, Researchers, Academics, Students

- **Long Tagline:**
IMPULSE unveils groundbreaking digitisation processes and immersive educational prototypes, advancing future literacy in academia. Engage with digitised cultural heritage transformed through cutting-edge technology, fostering innovative research and transformative learning experiences.
- **Short Tagline:**
Digitising the Future of Learning to connect CH and new tech.

Policy Makers, Decision-Makers, European Networks

- **Long Tagline:**
IMPULSE is shaping the future of cultural heritage policy, focusing on interoperability and sustainable digital practices. Contribute to the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage, guiding the integration of immersive digital experiences into mainstream cultural preservation and education.

- **Short Tagline:**
Pioneering Policies for Digital Cultural Heritage.

CCSI Organisations and Networks, Freelancers, Designers, and Artists

- **Long Tagline:**
IMPULSE is a catalyst for creativity, inviting CCSI stakeholders to explore the intersection of culture and innovation. Discover new dimensions in creative expression by upcycling digital heritage into captivating immersive environments.
- **Short Tagline:**
Creative Cultures Reimagined
- **A Cultural Heritage Metaverse or Towards a Heritage Metaverse**

GLAMs (Museums, Libraries, Archives, Cultural Heritage Holders)

- **Long Tagline:**
IMPULSE empowers GLAMs to redefine cultural engagement, preserving humanities collections through innovative digital strategies. Experience heritage a new, enhancing access and facilitating research and education in dynamic, immersive formats
- **Short Tagline:**
Heritage Transformed for Tomorrow

Non-users

- **Long Tagline:**
IMPULSE activates a knowledge building process by adopting user-friendly interactions and exploring different mediums of communication.
- **Short Tagline:**
New audiences in the Heritage Multiverse

These taglines have been designed to resonate with the specific interests and aspirations of each target audience while capturing the essence of the IMPULSE project's innovative approach to cultural heritage digitisation and immersive technologies.

List of Hashtags (max 10)

The following list of hashtags has been drawn from the brainstorming session held with the C&D Team. As partner representatives discussed the main themes composing the multifaceted expertise IMPULSE is made of, a preliminary list of hashtags was presented. The starting list has been submitted to a popularity check on online platforms.

After discussion, the following set of hashtags (highlighted in bold) have been selected by the C&D Team to tag IMPULSE's communication and dissemination content:

#immersiveDigitisation
#DigitalCulturalHeritage
#DigitalCreativity

#upcycling
 #UpcyclingCulturalHeritage
#CreativeUpcycling

#Metaverse
 #heritageMetaverse
#immersiveNarratives
 #heritageoftomorrow
#IMPULSECommunityOfPractice

#EducationOfTheFuture

#ImmersiveEducation
#LifelongLearning
 #DigitisedHeritageModules

2.4.4 Languages

For the IMPULSE project, a multilingual approach to communication and dissemination content is essential to ensure broad accessibility and engagement. This section of the C&D Strategy emphasises the importance of language inclusivity:

- **Primary language - English:** English serves as the primary language for the IMPULSE project's dissemination and communication. This choice caters to a global audience, ensuring widespread reach and facilitating international collaborations. Key documents, website and social media content, official communications, and major publications will be primarily in English.
 - **Multilingual Approach with Partners' Languages:** Recognising the diverse linguistic backgrounds of the project's partners and their respective communities, content will also be made available in the languages of all partner countries. This inclusive approach ensures that the project's findings, updates, and communications are accessible to non-English speaking stakeholders, enhancing local engagement and participation. Particularly, communication and dissemination content will be available in the following languages:

- Polish;
- German;
- Italian;
- Maltese;
- Greek.

Through this multilingual strategy, the IMPULSE project recognises diversity of languages and cultures as vectors for engagement, inclusion, and the overall democratisation of access to knowledge. This approach aligns with the project's commitment to diversity and inclusivity, aiming maximising its impact and outreach.

2.5 Communication and Dissemination Management Process

2.5.1 Timeline

Figure 5. Gantt diagram comparing the projects' main touchpoints with C&D Streams unpacked along channels (website, social media, newsletter, collaborative ppace), and C&D Team activities (Sharing analytics).

2.5.2 Collaborative model

By framing communication and dissemination activities as transversal processes, crossing all WPs and benefitting from all partners expert inputs, the C&D Strategy relies on a collaborative model. Such a model sparks from the establishment of

a Communication and Dissemination Team, constituted by WP5 DISS Lead partner – UNIBO – and one or more representatives each partner involved in IMPULSE. The C&D Team embodies the main actor for communication and dissemination activities, working by a collaborative model that is structured around three main pillars:

1. **A fluid data and information sharing among partners:** the C&D Team will regularly meet to co-create, co-define, collect, and discuss inputs to better inform communication and dissemination activities. This responds to an adaptive C&D strategy, that will develop along overlapping Streams: such a configuration invites feedback loops and adjustments to the set of actions to be taken in connection to communication and dissemination updated needs.
2. **ImCO as ambassadors of IMPULSE messages:** The IMPULSE Community of Practice will be at first represented by IMPULSE partners, who will play the role of ambassadors in delivering key concepts, messages, as well as results and achievements as long as the project unfolds.
3. **An adaptable and transformative model** according to the IMPULSE communities' specific needs.

2.5.3 Communication & Dissemination Team Responsibilities

According to the three-pillared collaborative model, the responsibilities of the Communication & Dissemination Team are designed to ensure effective, cohesive, and far-reaching communication and dissemination efforts. Here's an overview of their key responsibilities:

- **Content Development and Management:** Create, curate, and manage communication and dissemination content according to the project's visual and editorial guidelines (see section 4), ensuring they are accurate, engaging, and tailored to the project's diverse audiences. This includes overseeing the production of digital content, press releases, educational materials, and promotional assets.
- **Ensuring consistency:** Maintain the consistency of messaging across all platforms and activities, adhering to the project's visual and editorial guidelines (see section 4), and conveying the project's key messages in the set tone of voice (see section 2.3.4). This means also ensuring that events (such as workshops, conferences, and other activities) that are integral to the project's communication and dissemination activities are coordinated and publicised according to the project's C&D strategy.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** Identify and engage with key stakeholders each partner is already connected with, to ensure broader reach to the IMPULSE project. Key out-of-target stakeholders might include academia, cultural institutions, policy makers, and the civil society. Each partner can

tailor a “local” communication strategy to establish and nurture loops of relationships aiming at amplifying the project’s reach and impact.

- **Digital Presence Management:** According to the C&D Commitment to sustainability (see section 1.4), the C&D Team will be asked to curate the project’s digital presence, including partner’s own websites and social media platforms, ensuring content published there is up to date, engaging, and effectively reaching target audiences.
- **Cross-Work Package Collaboration for Communication and Dissemination activities:** Work closely with leaders and teams across all work packages to gather insights, updates, and results, as well as looking for opportunities to disseminate and invite academic and expert discussions on the project’s achievements. This collaboration ensures that communication and dissemination activities will be continuously adjusted to the project’s progress.
- **Monitoring and Reporting:** Based on the KPIs set to assess the impact of communication and dissemination activities (see section 2.4.4), the C&D Team will be asked to regularly report (M7; M12; M24; M30; M36) to the WP5 lead partner, UNIBO, providing insights and recommendations for improvements. Furthermore, the C&D Team will be asked to provide feedback from communication and dissemination activities carried out on non-project channels to continually enhance communication strategies and tactics.

By undertaking these responsibilities, the Communication & Dissemination Team plays a crucial role in ensuring that the IMPULSE project’s discoveries, innovations, and insights are effectively communicated and disseminated, fostering broader understanding, engagement, and impact.

2.5.4 Monitoring (KPIs)

IMPULSE C&D KPIs are comprehensive of qualitative and quantitative indicators divided according to the three streams of the project.

KPI	M12	M24	M36
Stream 1. Awareness			
Social Media Followers	500	1000	2000
Newsletter subscribers	100	400	800
Europe-wide dissemination of IMPULSE	- Nr. Of Reposted links - Invitation to EU-Wide events on CH	- Nr. Of Application in IMPULSE initiatives (Hackatons, IMCo, etc.) and geographical distribution	

Stream 2. Fostering Engagement and Collaboration

Members of IMCo	50	100	250
Participants to the Hackathons	-	80	80
New Learning Modules adoption	-	200	500

Stream 3. Measuring Impact during and beyond the project

New ideas connected to XR tech in CH areas			Qualitative reports
IMPULSE events (and connected ones) attendance	-	Min 200 pp. per year	Min 250 pp. per year
New audience development	-		Qualitative reports
Increase of IMPULSE connection with other linked projects		2 joints initiatives per year	2 joints initiatives per year

Stream 4. Ensuring ongoing relevance and accessibility

Diffusion of Policy Briefs	-	More than 100 download	More than 200 download
Participants in Acceleration and Mentoring Programs	-		100
New HE/Erasmus+/Creative EU proposals in connection to IMPULSE		2	4

3 Channels

3.1 IMPULSE Communication Channels

According to the results of the preliminary survey (see section 2.1), IMPULSE's communication, engagement, and dissemination actions will be delivered in the following set of channels:

- IMPULSE Website;
- IMPULSE Social Media channels;
- **IMPULSE Collaborative Space**, to be activated concurrently to key events in the project's roadmap.

This set has been tuned to the partners most frequently used platforms and defined according to the most suitable channels to reach out to IMPULSE's target audiences.

A fourth and additional channel might be embodied by the setting-up of the Metaverse environment, which might contribute to Stream 4: Ensuring ongoing relevance and accessibility (see section 2.1) of the project's main findings and achievements, delivering them in an experienceable format.

3.1.1 IMPULSE Website

The IMPULSE's website represents the main communication tool of the project as it is the main source of information about the project, its objectives, activities, and results, alongside the project's social media channels. The website will be developed by WP5 Lead partner, UNIBO, to implement communication and dissemination activities. Furthermore, the website will work as a repository for information on activities and knowledge-sharing of results. The website will be linked to the main outputs of the project, whose relevance to communication and dissemination aims will be constantly co-defined by the C&D Team.

The website structure can be adjusted throughout the project. However, coverage of the following elements will be ensured:

- *Home Page/About IMPULSE*
- *Newsletter, history of newsletters, leads and creation of events*
- *Tools and educational resources / educational Toolbox / Services and tools*
- *Connection with collaborative spaces*
- *Media/Publications*
- *Contact us*

The website is to be regularly updated to fit the project's advancements and keep the public and community informed about any relevant event or outcomes. Therefore, the website also serves as a reference for the project's development.

The IMPULSE website will be a central point for the whole dissemination strategy, being a hub of information about the project's proposal and objectives, along with news and all the resources for partners and target audiences.

3.1.2 IMPULSE Social Media Channels

As for social media platforms, they support the C&D Strategy in establishing a direct and faster-paced link of communication with diverse audiences, contributing to building and maintaining attention on the projects' actions.

In order to ensure the project's online presence and to reach the target audience, three different social media channels were set up (LinkedIn, Instagram, X/Twitter), which allows for a more targeted and community-specific sharing of the project's activities. Partners and members of the IMPULSE consortium are also responsible for liking, sharing, and reposting the project's posts on the social media channels to reach a wider audience. By providing the project with a dedicated profile on both LinkedIn and Instagram, the activation of "content amplification strategies" – namely sharing and re-posting content from and by partners – will be facilitated, resulting in a wider reach that leverages on the project's constituting network.

As such, social media channels have been created in March 2024. The Social Media media strategy for IMPULSE serves several purposes:

- Creating a positive message about IMPULSE and its results.
- Making the project visible online, disseminating news about project activities and achievements.
- Engaging people in online conversations to gain deeper insight into their views and feelings on the topics covered.
- Ensuring effective reporting of events.
- Supporting project networking, with special focus on the defined target audiences and areas of influence.

Proper use of hashtags ([see section 2.3.4](#)) is emphasised as it helps increase social media presence by making content viewable to anyone interested in the proposed hashtags, beyond just IMPULSE followers.

The suggested hashtags to be used in social media channels follow the whole dissemination strategy, including the alignment with the tone of voice, the keywords, and taglines, presented in previous chapters of this document.

Table of Social media profiles and links

LinkedIn Profile: @euimpulse

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euimpulse/>

Instagram Profile: @euimpulse

<https://www.instagram.com/euimpulse/>

X (Twitter) Profile: @euimpulse

<https://twitter.com/euimpulse>

3.1.3 Collaborative space

IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo) will benefit from the development and launch of a dedicated Collaborative space. According to project proposal, Mastodon was elected as a viable platform to host the IMCo. However, after further research, Mastodon presented microblogging features, making it more aligned to social media platforms like LinkedIn. The commitment to experiment Mastodon is supported by its open infrastructure that, in alignment with the positioning of IMPULSE project, might boost the project's content amplification strategies on a free and open-source software.

As such, the C&D Strategy will keep Mastodon as a side-channel of social media communication.

In addition, further research has been carried out to identify platforms that might be more suitable to engagement and bottom-up participation, in order to provide the IMCo with an online space enabling continuous communication within the community, in a forum-like format. Detailed information on the most suitable platform will be provided in D30, as it relates to setting-up of the digital co-working space of IMCo. The collaborative space responds to **Stream 2: Engaging for inclusivity, Cooperation and Collaboration**. As such, it can be framed as a community-based channel which will be activated concurrently with key events involving the IMCo: the pre-Hackathon phase and its three workshops (MS18), the Hackathon (MS19), primarily; a secondary set of events during which the collaborative space might be activated links to the launch of running pilots and prototypes (MS 2, 3, 4), the launch of the Acceleration & Mentoring Hub (D32), the Metaverse performance and exhibition (MS5, 6) and the final conference in Bologna (MS20).

3.1.4 Extra channels: Acceleration Mentoring Hub & Metaverse

Extra channels can be understood as the platforms participating in **Stream 4: Ensuring ongoing relevance and accessibility** (see [section 2.1](#)). These platforms aim at maintaining IMPULSE's main findings accessible beyond the project's duration. An example of extra channels is embodied in the Acceleration & Mentoring Hub, which will overgo the duration of the project for a higher impact and dissemination of IMPULSE action.

Furthermore, building on IMPULSE Metaverse Exhibition and Performance (MS5, 6), the virtual space that is going to host these events can be framed as extra communication channel, once it stays available for visitors to explore and learn about the project, its partners' collections and the broader impact of historic and contemporary didactic processes that emerged throughout the project.

3.2 External booster channels

In addition to the main IMPULSE communication channels, partners are invited to connect and interact via their own personal channels, framed here as “content amplifying” channels. These booster channels will intensify impact and increase interactions/engagement by mutual tagging and referencing.

3.2.1 Partners’ channels

According to the preliminary survey, IMPULSE partners’ channels fall into a diverse set of channels, among which websites, LinkedIn and Instagram cover most of their own communication actions.

Figure 6. Histogram resulting from the preliminary survey (see section 2.1) and showing partners’ own channels distribution.

As such, each partner will convey activities connected to the IMPULSE project on their main websites, LinkedIn and Instagram channels, maintaining the tone of voice and following the key concepts and messages illustrated above (see section 2). Communication content will be created and curated in compliance with the project’s visual identity guidelines and templates provided in the Communication & Dissemination Toolkit (see section 4).

3.3 E-Newsletter

The newsletter will allow subscribed audience and any interested individual to receive periodic updates about IMPULSE to reinforce the project's impact within its community and beyond. Particularly, it will serve as a reminder of the project's ongoing activities and achievements, contributing to maintaining engagement and interest over time. In fact, it will be sent at strategic intervals (see Figure 5 in section 2.6.1), providing updates on key points of interest (i.e. opening calls; deadline reminders; launching workshops and the hackaton event); as such the newsletter works as a tool for call to action, communicating invitations to upcoming events, opportunities for collaboration, or encouraging the interested audience to remain actively involved in the project.

IMPULSE's e-Newsletters will begin with **an editorial**, which will be prepared by a partner or a member of the project, and it will address a development of the project and/or a highlight of the project so far. The content of such an editorial will be discussed on a case-by-case basis.

Further, under **"IMPULSE's Highlights"**, the newsletter will provide a short description of IMPULSE's main activities and achievements. This will be followed by a section on **"Upcoming Events"** which will provide an overview of the events, organised by the project consortium or the consortium's partners and members that are in line with the theme of IMPULSE. The list of such events is kept on Teams WP6 folder and is to be updated by the partners and members of the consortium throughout the duration of the project. Last, a **"Contact Us"** section will be included.

Professional marketing platforms can be used to automate the distribution among contact points. Interested audience can subscribe to the newsletter via the project's website, and the newsletter will also be promoted through specific social media posts. Newsletters will be sent at strategic intervals to the community; *ad-hoc* editions will be sent occasionally to communicate adequately about specific activities or events.

3.4 Events

Events can be understood as additional channels to boost IMPULSE visibility, while setting-up conditions for engagement and further networking actions. The C&D Strategy frames events as two-way bridges: on one hand, IMPULSE might leverage on them to build connections with ongoing, concurrent events; on the other hand, ongoing, concurrent events might tap into IMPULSE's visibility for further interactions.

This framework relies on a collaborative understanding of communication and dissemination activities, providing partners with the opportunity to constantly share information on events occurring within their own networks, that might resonate with IMPULSE's main research and innovation areas of concern.

3.4.1 C&D Event Form

With the aim of facilitating information collection on events and activities carried out within the partners' own networks, a survey-model will be designed and shared with the C&D Team. **Through the form, the C&D core team (WP5 lead partner UNIBO) promotes a structured workflow to receive information directly from the interested partner**, which will share details - text and pics - on events to be promoted. The C&D Form is an essential tool to IMPULSE's C&D Strategy, holding the potential to establish as a good practice in communication and dissemination actions.

The C&D Form will be shared on Teams for the duration of the project. The link will be also shared in and accessible by the IMPULSE Repository (Teams), under WP5 channel.

3.5 Open Science Practices

IMPULSE will apply the Open Access and Open Data and will fully align to the Open Science principle of Horizon Europe, and the Open Science strategy will be mainly based on:

- ensuring the open access obligations whilst properly managing the intellectual property rights of the beneficiaries, implementing a findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data management, as described below, and the principle of open by default for all data which does not involve commercial exploitation;
- ensuring the sharing of research outputs as early and widely as possible;
- engaging local CCI value chains actors in the implementation of the responsible research and innovation foreseen in the project. In line with its guiding principles, IMPULSE endorses the values of quality and integrity, collective benefit, equity and fairness, diversity, and inclusiveness. It will follow the guiding principles of P2P, transparency, scrutiny, critique and reproducibility, equality of opportunities, responsibility, respect and accountability, collaboration, participation and inclusion, flexibility, and sustainability. In line with the recommendation, it will encourage “bibliodiversity”, through the use of diverse formats and means of publications, and open science communication by disseminating the project results towards other research fields, decision makers and the public at large.

In line with the principles of Open Access, **central to the C&D strategy is the creation and maintenance of a Data Management Plan (DMP)** that articulates **clear policies on data handling** according to the **FAIR principles** —ensuring data is **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**. The DMP underscores IMPULSE’s commitment to transparency by detailing the conditions under which data is accessible, thus balancing openness with necessary restrictions to safeguard sensitive information. Regular updates to the DMP ensure it remains aligned with project objectives and compliance requirements.

Data is deposited in certified repositories that guarantee long-term preservation, unique identification, and controlled access, aligning with the principle that data should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”¹. Furthermore, the project facilitates the reuse and validation of data by providing comprehensive metadata and supporting information, thereby enhancing the integrity and utility of the research outputs.

A more detailed coverage in these matters will be provided and updated concurrently to the submission of D34 (Data Management Plan, JU) and **D35** (Open Research Data Pilot, JU and UNIBO).

¹ European Commission. Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. Version 3.0. 26 July 2016.

4 Communication and Dissemination Toolkit

This chapter will present IMPULSE's visual identity, including a set of guidelines and resources for such an identity, namely logo, templates, colour scheme, and typography.

4.1 Visual Identity

Recognising the significance of a distinct visual identity for its branding, the IMPULSE consortium identified major elements that are core to the project's message and identity and brought them together to create the project's logo and the overall image. Therefore, for IMPULSE to be different from other projects, a visual identity has been developed, and is therefore to be used by all consortium partners and members in any kind of communications, either internal or external. This will allow the project to have its own identity, to be distinguished from others and easily recognisable by all target stakeholders – to have its own identity.

4.1.1 Logo

The logo has been created keeping in mind the importance of training, connections and the ecosystem of Earth and Space. **The training and diversity dimension** was shown through multi-coloured pillars which symbolise diversity in training, representing varied educational dimensions and inclusivity, essential for cultivating skills in the dynamic space sector. In addition, **dot connections** exemplify collaboration among users and industry actors, illustrating the project's emphasis on fostering connections, knowledge sharing, and collaborative learning in the space education ecosystem. At last, **ecosystem, consisting of Earth and Space**, underscores the interconnectedness among various aspects of the space industry and education, fostering a synergistic environment for skill and educational development.

Elements of the logo:

Logo (with different colour versions):

4.1.2 Colour Scheme

The colours have been selected among the brighter range of nuances, to grant the project a vibrant and lively identity. The colours come in a triadic distribution, recalling the Cyan-Magenta-Yellow (CMY) colour model, as a detail appealing to digital workspaces.

WAVY PINK
#E4509D

IMPULSE YELLOW
#F9E041

IMMERSIVE BLUE
#72CEE1

4.1.3 Typography

The font used for titles and subtitles is “**Ubuntu**” in bold and regular weight, respectively, and for body of text “Open Sans” in regular weight, as shown in the following table:

Title
Subtitle
Text

4.1.4 Templates: Print and Digital promotion materials

This chapter outlines the creation of an initial collection of print and digital promotional materials for various events and channels. The initial promotional materials are to be updated throughout the project. Those include a brochure template, poster, roll-up, roll-up wall and a press release template. Additional promotional material might be prepared throughout the duration of the project. If needed. Such promotional materials will be provided to the partners by UNIBO in a digital format (e-documents). Major documents will be available online either on the website or on Teams WP5 Channel and dedicated folders.

Brochures will be presented as A4, foldable documents and will highlight main information about IMPULSE’s objectives, partners, activities and later, results. The text on the brochure is easy to read and the brochure itself is visually appealing in order to attract readers and generate interest in the project. Its content will be updated alongside the project’s development and tailored to specific events, where IMPULSE will be promoted, if needed. If needed, the materials can be translated into other (also local) languages, by appropriate partners. Translated content will be transmitted in a timely manner by consortium partners to UNIBO, which will oversee the editing of the material and its distribution.

Roll-ups will serve as a visual support to promote IMPULSE during various internal and external event and highlight key project information, including the members and partners of the consortium, the project’s main activities and objectives. The aim of the roll-up is to capture the public’s attention and generate interest in the project, with the aim of increasing the visibility and reach of the project. The roll-up template will be provided in English only.

Posters will primarily serve as a visual aid during scientific events to promote IMPULSE's methodology and highlight key project information.

All templates have been shared in the IMPULSE's dedicated Repository (Microsoft Teams), under WP5 channel folders.

4.2 Data-based artifacts protocol

This protocol applies to all graphic data-based artifacts (e.g. graphs, visualisation, diagrams, etc.) produced in the context of IMPULSE. **To ensure the compliance with FAIR principles of data management, all data-based artifacts (e.g. graphs, visualisation) produced within the project will be published along with the reference of the data source used for its creation.** The data source should lead to an open access file in a machine readable format depending on data type (e.g. cvs, tsv, geo, json, etc).

To ensure accessibility, the data source will be published both in its complete form, and in an aggregated form used to make the visualisation or data artifact.

To ensure visual coherence, **all data-based artifacts will be compliant with the IMPULSE Visual Identity** (see [section 4](#)).

IMPULSE

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